

E-Content

Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

Vidya-mitra is an online learning portal for all the e-content projects developed under the NME-ICT (National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology), MHRD.

Content Creator

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Instructions for E-Content Exploration:

Dear Learners,

Welcome to the course! The e-content is organized into **two modules**, with each module divided into **four interactive quadrants**

Quadrant 01: E-Text Content

Quadrant 02: Summary

Quadrant 03: Self-Assessment

Quadrant 04: Web Resources

How to Navigate the Course:

Each quadrant includes **clickable icons**. And Search **“Anjuman”** in Institution Only

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Note: Follow the sequence of quadrants for maximum learning benefit.

Happy learning!

Module-5: Basic Molecular Technique

Project : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

Course : B.Sc 1st year/ Course 1

Subject : Botany

PI Name : Dr. Amanulla Khan

Institute : Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science

Available in : English

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Module-6: Soil Analysis Techniques

Project : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

Course : B.Sc 1st year/ Course 1

Subject : Botany

PI Name : Dr. Amanulla Khan

Institute : Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science

Available in : English

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Module-7: Computer Techniques

Project : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

Course : B.Sc 1st year/ Course 1

Subject : Botany

PI Name : Dr. Amanulla Khan

Institute : Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science

Available in : English

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Quadrant 01: E-Text Content

Quadrant 02: Self-Assessment

Title : Module-2: Microscopy and Staining Techniques

Course : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science
Level of course : Other
Project : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

E-Text Self-Assessment

Title : Module-4: Biochemical Analysis

Course : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science
Level of course : Other
Project : Tools and Techniques in Plant Science

E-Text Self-Assessment

The screenshot shows the VIDYA-MITRA e-content portal interface. At the top, the logo and navigation menu are visible. The main content area displays the title 'Module-6: Soll Analysis Techniques'. Below this, course details are listed: 'Tools and Techniques in Plant Science' for the course, 'Other' for the level, and 'Tools and Techniques in Plant Science' for the project. A 'Self-Assessment' section is highlighted in red. A browser window preview shows the content creator's information: 'Module's Name: Soll Analysis Techniques', 'Content Creator Summary', and 'Dr. Amanulla Khan, Department of Botany, Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science, Murud-Janjira, Raigad Maharashtra-402401 India, E-mail ID: dramanullak@gmail.com'.

Quadrant 03: Summary

The screenshot shows the VIDYA-MITRA e-content portal interface. At the top, the logo and navigation menu are visible. The main content area displays the title 'Module-6: Biochemical Analysis'. Below this, course details are listed: 'Tools and Techniques in Plant Science' for the course, 'Other' for the level, and 'Tools and Techniques in Plant Science' for the project. A 'Self-Assessment' section is highlighted in red. A browser window preview shows the content creator's information: 'Module's Name: Biochemical Analysis', 'Web Resource', 'Content Creator', and 'Dr. Amanulla Khan, Department of Botany, Anjuman Islam Janjira, Degree College of Science, Murud-Janjira, Raigad Maharashtra-402401 India, E-mail ID: dramanullak@gmail.com'.

Quadrant 04: Web Resources

Module 01

Module 3

Module 5

Module 7

Module 02

Module 4

Module 6

I sincerely thank the *Vidya Mitra* Portal and Team for approving and uploading my educational e-content. This resource, now accessible to students and educators, aims to support self-learning under the NEP framework. Grateful for the opportunity to contribute to open academic knowledge.

Content Creator:

Dr. Amanulla Khan

Department of Botany

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